

REDUCTION OF SHOCK WAVE AMPLIFICATION IN MULTIPLE BALLISTIC FABRIC LAYER SYSTEMS

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1 Introduction

In the literature numerous experimental evidences have been reported in regards to amplification of transmitted peak pressures of blast/shock waves through flexible body armors made from multiple layers of ballistic protection fabric. An overview of relevant articles in this field is given e.g. by Zhu et al [1], Skews et al [2] and Hattingh et al [3]. The multiple layer effect was believed to be one of several factors causing the peak pressure amplification phenomenon [1]. By decreasing the air gap within the fabric layers by pre-compression, the pressure amplification may be reduced [4]. Instead of using pre-compression, a more practical approach is investigated in the present work, i.e., by means of a thin adhesive film placed in between the layers of ballistic fabric. The amplification properties of the bonded fabrics (with the adhesive film) are studied experimentally by using a compressed gas driven shock tube and the results are then compared to those of simply stacked fabrics (without the adhesive). Other alternative approaches for pre-compression, such as vacuum assisted fabric pre-compression and stitching, are also explored.

2 Shock Tube Testing

2.1 Materials

Three ballistic fabrics were examined: Twaron T717 plain woven fabric, Twaron UD41 and Spectra Shield SA-1211 unidirectional laminate fabrics. Their ply thicknesses are 0.389 mm, 0.238 mm and 0.125 mm with areal densities of 280 g/m², 238 g/m², and 95 g/m² respectively. Twaron T717 and Twaron UD41 were purchased from Teijin Aramid BV whereas the Spectra Shield SA-1211 was purchased from Honeywell International Inc. The adhesive film used to bond between fabric layers was 3M-9448HKB D/C Double-sided Tissue Tapes Black. Fig. 1 shows photograph and schematic representation of the ballistic fabrics.

Fig. 1. Ballistic fabrics: (a) Twaron T717, (b) Twaron UD41, (c) Spectra Shield SA-1211.

2.2 Approach

Fig. 2 shows our shock tube facility. The shock tube has a total length of 4.7 m and consists of a 1.3 m long driver section, 3.3 m long driven section, and 0.1 m muzzle section. Their inner diameter and wall thickness are 58.4 mm and 15.2 mm, respectively. The driver section is pressurized with Helium until the diaphragm is ruptured releasing a shock wave through the driven and muzzle sections towards the tested specimen. Mylar sheets were selected as the diaphragms due to their strength and ability to burst at a consistent pressure. The burst pressure at which the Mylar ruptured was recorded using a digital pressure gauge (Ashcroft D1005PS).

The specimens were mounted at the exit of the muzzle section. A circular plate made of 30 mm thick stainless steel (316L grade) was used to support the specimens. Two pressure transducers (Kistler 603B) were utilized to monitor the pressure profile of the generated shock wave. One pressure transducer mounted on the muzzle sidewall allowed the side-on shock wave profile near the exit (i.e. before the tested specimen) to be recorded. Another pressure transducer was mounted on the support plate and face-on to the shock wave (i.e. behind the tested specimen). The signals were sent through a signal conditioner and amplifier (Kistler 5015 charge meter) before being recorded by the GW Instek GDS-3154 oscilloscope. Fig. 3 shows experimental setup to measure the transmitted overpressure of the specimens. All specimens were subjected to the same side-on shock wave magnitude of approximately 186 kPa produced by bursting a 0.1 mm thick Mylar diaphragm.

Fig. 2. Shock tube facility (Impact Mechanics Laboratory, National University of Singapore).

Fig. 3. Setup for measuring transmitted overpressure of specimens.

3 Results

3.1 Stacked Fabric

Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of simply stacked Twaron T717 woven fabric are shown in Fig. 4. A typical reference trace (bare surface), obtained when no specimen was present over the support plate, shows a typical step pressure rise resulting from head-on impact of a plane shock wave on a flat surface. Four fabric stacks of 5, 15, 30, and 45 plies were tested in order to investigate the effect of number of layers on the shock wave transmission. The test results show that the peak pressures of Twaron T717 specimens are higher than that of the bare surface and the peak pressure increases with increasing number of Twaron T717 layers. Not surprisingly, the occurrence of the peak pressure is delayed as the number of Twaron T717 layers increases. A similar trend is observed for multiple layers of neat Twaron UD 41 and Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate specimens as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. The mean and standard deviation values for their peak pressures (in MPa) are 1.474 ± 0.078 , 1.891 ± 0.087 , 1.942 ± 0.248 , 2.052 ± 0.182 for 5, 15, 30, 45 layers of Twaron

T717, respectively; 1.275 ± 0.044 , 2.326 ± 0.256 , 2.799 ± 0.139 , 2.630 ± 0.232 for 5, 15, 30, 45 layers of Twaron UD41, respectively; 1.083 ± 0.290 , 1.626 ± 0.066 , 2.220 ± 0.040 , 2.778 ± 0.093 for 5, 15, 30, 45 layers of Spectra Shield SA-1211, respectively; and 0.747 ± 0.038 for the bare surface.

Fig. 4. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of stacked Twaron T717 woven fabric.

Fig. 5. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of stacked Twaron UD41 laminate fabric.

Fig. 6. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of stacked Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate fabric.

3.2 Bonded Fabric

When a bonded Twaron T717 fabric specimen is placed over the support plate and a shock wave released, the face-on pressure history is modified as illustrated in Fig. 7. It can be seen in this plot that the peak pressure has been greatly reduced, close to the peak pressure of the reference/bare surface. A similar trend is observed for multiple layers of bonded Twaron UD 41 and Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate specimens as shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. The mean and standard deviation values for their peak pressures (in MPa) are 0.765 ± 0.035 , 0.861 ± 0.060 , 0.907 ± 0.110 , 0.942 ± 0.018 for 5, 15, 30, and 45 layers of bonded Twaron T717, respectively; 0.965 ± 0.191 ; 1.463 ± 0.166 ; 1.624 ± 0.114 ; 1.700 ± 0.093 for 5, 15, 30, and 45 layers of bonded Twaron UD41, respectively; and 0.666 ± 0.068 , 0.841 ± 0.061 , 0.879 ± 0.176 , 0.956 ± 0.197 for 5, 15, 30, and 45 layers of bonded Spectra Shield SA-1211, respectively.

Fig. 7. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of bonded Twaron T717 woven fabric.

Fig. 9. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of bonded Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate fabric.

Fig. 8. Typical face-on pressure traces for multiple layers of bonded Twaron UD41 laminate fabric.

To quantitatively evaluate the relative effectiveness of different multiple ballistic fabric layer systems for blast/shock wave overpressure protection, a peak pressure amplification factor is used as a parameter. The peak pressure amplification factor is defined as the ratio of peak face-on pressure with specimen present to that of bare surface (without specimen present) [1,4].

Fig. 10 through Fig. 12 show the trend of peak pressure amplification factor as a function of number of fabric layers for simply stacked and bonded Twaron T717, Twaron UD41, Spectra Shield SA-1211 specimens, respectively. It can be seen in the figures that all stacked ballistic fabrics tested serve to amplify the peak pressure of the shock wave loading. Their amplification factor increases with increasing the number of their layers. Even at relatively thin fabric stack (5 layers), the peak pressure amplification factor can reach a value of 1.972 ± 0.104 , 1.706 ± 0.059 , and 1.448 ± 0.388 for stacked Twaron T717, stacked Twaron UD41, and stacked Spectra Shield SA-1211, respectively. At relatively thick fabric stack (45 layers), the peak pressure amplification factor reaches higher value, i.e., 2.745 ± 0.244 for stacked Twaron T717, 3.518 ± 0.311 for stacked Twaron UD41, and 3.716 ± 0.125 for stacked Spectra Shield SA-1211.

Interestingly, the bonded ballistic fabrics are able to reduce the shock wave amplification greatly. The value of their peak pressure amplification factor is relatively low, i.e., 1.024 ± 0.047 , 1.290 ± 0.255 , 0.891 ± 0.091 for 5 layers of bonded Twaron T717, bonded Twaron UD41, and bonded Spectra Shield SA-1211, respectively. At thicker layers (45 layers), the amplification factor is still relatively low, i.e., 1.261 ± 0.024 , 2.275 ± 0.124 , 1.279 ± 0.264 for bonded Twaron T717, bonded Twaron UD41, and bonded Spectra Shield SA-1211, respectively. This result demonstrates that the bonding with adhesive films effectively decreases or eliminates the air gap within the multiple layers of fabrics, thus increasing the apparent bulk density of the fabrics. It has been suggested by Gibson [4] that for materials with lower density, multiple layers make them easier to be compressed. The shock wave decelerates as the material is compressed, thus letting more compression waves to add to the shock wave strength, thereby increasing the peak pressure.

Fig. 11. Peak pressure amplification values for multiple layers of stacked and bonded Twaron UD41.

Fig. 10. Peak pressure amplification values for multiple layers of stacked and bonded Twaron T717.

Fig. 12. Peak pressure amplification values for multiple layers of stacked and bonded Spectra Shield SA-1211.

To assess whether the material of the adhesive film also contributes to the reduction of pressure amplification, multiple layers of the film were subjected to the same shock wave strength. Fig. 13

illustrates its pressure amplification factor as a function of its number of layers. It is obvious that the value of peak pressure amplification factor is close to 1 for a thick stack adhesive films (i.e. 45 layers) meaning that the shock wave is transmitted through the material without any pressure amplification or reduction. The amplification value slightly less than 1, i.e., a marginal attenuation of the transmitted shock wave, for thin stacks of film (i.e. less than 45 layers). Therefore, the material of the flexible adhesive film may have a slight additional contribution to the reduction of the peak pressure amplification in the bonded fabrics with fewer layers.

Fig. 13. Peak pressure amplification values for multiple layers of 3M-9448HKB D/C Tissue Tapes Black.

3.3 Vacuum Assisted Fabric Pre-compression

To investigate further whether removing the air gap within the fabric layers is really the main factor related to the reduction in pressure amplification, a pre-compression through use of a vacuum (referred as Vacuum Assisted Fabric Pre-compression, VAFP) was used rather than the adhesive film or gauze net used by Gibson. In this VAFP experimental setup (Fig. 14), a Twaron T717 stack of 5 layers was placed within bagging films, and sealed using a sealant tape. The sealed fabric stack was then fixed to the support plate of the shock tube. After connecting the sealed fabric stack with a

vacuum pump and applying vacuum, a shock wave with the same magnitude was employed to the fabric stack. As usual, the experiment was repeated three times to check for consistency.

Fig. 14. Experimental setup for Vacuum Assisted Fabric Pre-compression (VAFP).

Fig. 15 presents a comparison of peak pressure amplification factor for 5 layers of stacked, VAFP, and bonded Twaron T717 subjected to the same shock wave strength. The neat Twaron T717 stack exhibits the highest peak pressure amplification factor. By placing flexible adhesive films in between the layers of Twaron T717 (bonded Twaron T717 stack), the pressure amplification is successfully eliminated, i.e., the value of amplification factor is about 1. As expected, the VAFP Twaron T717 gives a similar effect. Its pressure amplification factor is in good agreement with the bonded system. Again, the elimination or reduction of pressure amplification for VAFP and modified fabrics is due to the increase in apparent bulk density of the fabrics meaning that the fabrics become more difficult to compress. In this case, the shock wave does not slow down, thus preventing compression waves to add to the shock wave strength, thereby eliminating the increase in peak pressure. As shown in Fig. 16, the shock wave

is markedly delayed due to the presence of the simply stacked fabric. In contrast, when either the bonded or VAFP fabric system is tested, the shock wave delay is greatly reduced. Regarding the fact that the amplification factor of the bonded fabric is slightly lower than the VAFP one, it can be due to the additional contribution from the shock wave attenuation property of the double-sided adhesive material used as previously discussed in section 3.2 or the difficulty in maintaining the partial vacuum for the VAFP system.

Fig. 15. Peak pressure amplification values for 5 layers of stacked, VAFP, and bonded Twaron T717.

Fig. 16. Typical face-on pressure traces for 5 layers of neat, VAFP, and modified Twaron T717.

3.4 Stitched Fabric

Besides the use of the double-sided adhesive tape (modified) and VAFP fabric approaches, removing/decreasing air gap within the fabric layers may be performed by employing stitching. This approach has advantages over the others such as less weight addition and maintaining flexibility. However, the stitching process may become more difficult for very thick ballistic fabric stacks. Fig. 17 shows a photograph of the specimens. Each specimen consisted of 5 layers of fabric stitched longitudinally and transversely with Kevlar yarn. The stitch space and stitch pitch were set at 5 mm and 4 mm, respectively.

Fig. 17. Photograph of stitched fabric specimens.

A comparison of peak pressure amplification factor for the stitched, modified, and neat fabric stacks of Twaron T717, Twaron UD41, and Spectra Shield SA-1211 is shown in Fig. 18, Fig. 19, and Fig. 20, respectively. For Twaron T717 plain woven fabric, the pressure amplification factor for the stitched fabric is much lower than the stacked one. Its value is in very good agreement with the VAFP result given in Fig. 15, but slightly higher compared to the pressure amplification of the bonded one. Again, it is possibly due to the additional contribution from shock wave attenuation property of the adhesive tape in the bonded fabric.

The stitched Twaron UD41 and Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate fabrics also reduce the pressure amplification but are not as effective as the stitched Twaron T717. Their amplification factors are only slightly lower than the simply stacked fabrics and the values are too high compared with the bonded ones. The reasons for this are still not understood, but may include fabric structure (e.g., weave architecture vs laminates), fabric thickness, stitch space, stitch pitch, and thread tension.

Fig. 18. Peak pressure amplification values for 5 layers of stacked, stitched, and bonded Twaron T717.

Fig. 19. Peak pressure amplification values for 5 layers of neat, stitched, and modified Twaron UD41.

Fig. 20. Peak pressure amplification values for 5 layers of neat, stitched, and modified Spectra Shield.

4 Conclusions

Our experimental results demonstrate that bonding layers of fabric or laminates with flexible adhesive films is a practical alternative to gauze net pre-compression in effectively reducing or eliminating the shock wave amplification of multiple layers of ballistic fabric. It has been verified through a vacuum assisted fabric pre-compression (VAFP) experiment that the reduction in pressure amplification is due to the removal of air gap within the multiple layers of fabric, thus increasing the apparent bulk density of the fabric. Besides using adhesive films, we have proposed stitching as an alternative method to reduce or eliminate the pressure amplification behavior. Stitching approach has advantages over the use of adhesive films such as less weight addition and less reduction in flexibility. Among the ballistic fabrics we tested, stitching is the most effective for Twaron T717 plain woven fabric. Further experimental investigations are needed to understand why stitching is less effective for Twaron UD41 and Spectra Shield SA-1211 laminate fabrics, and also to explore how the effectiveness of stitching for these fabrics can be further improved.

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